

CORROSION RATE MEASUREMENT OF SHEET PILE WALL IN THE PORT OF DURBAN

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ABSTRACT

Background: Harbors provide shelter for vessels, whereas ports facilitate the docking of ships that transport passengers and cargo (Jellett 2024). The Port of Durban relies on steel sheet piles to protect quay walls from rising sea level and erosion. Understanding the corrosion rate is crucial for maintaining these structures.

Objectives: This study aimed to assess the corrosion rates and estimate the remaining thickness of steel sheet pile walls at the Island View Berth 3 and Maydon Wharf Berth 12.

Methods: Ultrasonic thickness (UT) gauges were employed to measure the remaining thickness of steel sheet piles. Corrosion rates were calculated using the formula $icorr = (T_o - T_a)/t$, where T_o is the original thickness, T_a is the actual thickness, and t is the exposure time in years. Additional laboratory analyses of chloride content and pH levels were conducted to evaluate the impact of the marine environment on corrosion.

Results: At Island View Berth 3, the average corrosion rate was 0.0516 mm/year 28 years after installation. At Maydon Wharf Berth 12, the corrosion rates vary by zone: 0.0545 mm/year in the splash zone, 0.0485 mm/year in the tidal zone, 0.0345 mm/year in the low-water zone, and 0.0290 mm/year in the immersion zone, yielding an overall corrosion rate of 0.0466 mm/year.

Conclusions: This study highlights the significant corrosion variability across different zones and emphasizes the need for a comprehensive maintenance plan to address deterioration. These findings provide essential insights for future design and preservation strategies of marine structures at the Port of Durban.

Keywords: Corrosion, Sheet piles, Corrosion rate, Quay wall, Port of Durban

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Zikhali and Setaka (2019) stated that many of today's quay walls, such as those at the Port of Durban, are old and last decades. However, the ever-increasing global trade and growing volumes of cargo, along with larger modern vessels, place rising demands on these quay walls. Additionally, quay walls and infrastructure are typically exposed to corrosion, which can severely impact infrastructure. Valdez et al. (2016) mentioned that corrosion and pollution are harmful processes that degrade the environmental quality and compromise the longevity of marine structures and materials. Therefore, to ensure the protection of people and areas surrounding ports, it is crucial that the existing quay walls remain structurally sound and continue to function effectively.

1.2. Problem Statement

Corrosion significantly compromises the structural integrity and longevity of marine structures, particularly in high-salinity environments (Xia et al. 2024). The Island View sheet-pile wall is essential for the operational safety of the Port of Durban. Understanding the corrosion rates of these structures is vital for the development of effective maintenance strategies.

1.3. Objectives

This study focuses on the corrosion rate measurement of an Island View sheet pile wall to provide insights into the current state of this important maritime structure. By examining the methodologies used to assess corrosion and analyzing the resulting data, we seek to enhance the knowledge of the factors influencing corrosion rates and propose strategies for mitigating its impact. Through comprehensive evaluation, this study contributes valuable information to the fields of civil engineering and maritime infrastructure management.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Corrosion in marine environments has been extensively studied because of its significant impact on the durability and safety of maritime infrastructures. The corrosion of sheet piles, particularly in port structures, is a well-documented issue that affects both the structural integrity and maintenance costs.

2.1. Corrosion in Marine Environments

The North American Steel Sheet Piling Association (n.d.) has stated that corrosion is a natural electrochemical process that affects all steels to various degrees. It occurs similarly to a battery, with an electric current flowing between the positive electrode (anode) and the negative electrode (cathode) in the presence of an electrolyte, usually water. As the current moves from the anode to the cathode, the anode (steel) corrodes, leading to rust formation. Corrosion is a design issue for steel sheet piles because the anticipated loss in thickness over the lifespan of a structure affects its structural capacity.

Dantas et al. (2024) stated that marine environments involve several exposed zones with different degrees of aggressiveness, and that the corrosion performance of marine steel sheet pile structures in each zone requires separate attention. Therefore, the corrosion rate on the steel sheet pile surface is typically different in each zone. The average corrosion rate profile of steel sheet piles in most marine environment installations is shown in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Marine environment zones and corrosion attack variation between them

Source: A. Dantas et al. (2024)

2.2. Case Studies and Applications

Several case studies have demonstrated the impact of environmental conditions on corrosion rates. Wall and Wadsö (2013) noted significant variations based on local conditions. Protective measures such as concrete encasement and cathodic protection are common strategies for combating corrosion (RPI Construction Equipment 2022).

2.3. Corrosion Mitigation

Mitigating corrosion in sheet-pile walls requires preventive and corrective measures. Malu (n.d.) discussed various strategies for corrosion protection including the use of corrosion-resistant materials, protective coatings, and cathodic protection systems. The effectiveness of these strategies varies based on the environmental conditions and specific characteristics of the sheet pile wall. Concentrated salt-induced corrosion has been observed in marine environments worldwide.

Genin (2023) explained that protecting steel structures in marine environments involves a range of measures, such as (organic) coatings, corrosion allowances to reduce corrosion loss, and cathodic protection systems such as galvanic anode cathodic protection (GACP) or impressed current cathodic protection (ICCP). Furthermore, cathodic protection mitigates the high cost of steel and other alloys corroded in seawater (Googan 2022).

3. METHODS

According to Shen et al. (2023), several techniques such as electrochemical sensing technology, visual inspection, and weight loss measurement have been employed to measure corrosion rates in marine environments. These techniques, while straightforward, may lack precision and can be labor intensive. Solorzano (2018) conducted a study to measure the corrosion rate using ultrasonic thickness (UT) technology to measure the steel sheet pile thickness. The obtained results were used to calculate the corrosion rate using the following equation.

$$i_{corr} = (T_o - T_a)/t$$

where (T_o) - is the original thickness, (T_a) is the actual thickness, and (t) is the exposure time in years (y) .

4. RESULTS

4.1. Introduction

The results from inspections and measurements of steel sheet piles at Island View Berth 3 and Maydon Wharf Berth 12 in the Port of Durban include data on the remaining steel thickness of the sheet piles and the corrosion rates calculated from these measurements. Additionally, laboratory investigations of the chloride content and pH levels were conducted to understand the impact of the marine environment on corrosion processes. The results are presented in the tables and figures, followed by a discussion of the findings.

4.2. Island View Berth 3

Island View Berth 3, constructed in 1993, features ARBED BZ 7 steel sheet piles with an original thickness of 8 mm. Measurements of the remaining thickness were taken 28 years after installation. Figure 3.1 summarizes the recorded thicknesses of the steel sheet piles at various distances along the berth. The results show significant variability in the remaining thickness of the sheet piles, with a range of 3.0 mm to 8.0 mm.

Figure 3.1: Sheet Pile Thickness at 10m intervals

The average corrosion rate was calculated based on the difference between the original and remaining thicknesses using the formula, $i_{corr} = (T_o - T_a)/t$. Below Figure 3.2 show the different corrosion rate calculated in IV3.

Corrosion Rate Measurement of Sheet Pile Wall in the Port of Durban

Figure 3.2: Corrosion Rate at IV Berth 3

4.3. Maydon Wharf Berth 12

The sheet pile wall at Maydon Wharf Berth 12 was reconstructed in 2012 using a combination of HZ and AZ 18-700 steel sheet piles. The original thickness of the AZ 18-700 piles was 9 mm. Thickness measurements were performed 10 years after the installation.

The corrosion rate was measured 20 times at four different heights (4.5m, 5.8m, 8.5m & 10.5m) from the top of the pile to seabed level. The scatter plots below show the corrosion rate at each depth. At 4.5m depth, the corrosion rate decreased with increasing distance (Figure 3.3), at 5.8m depth, the corrosion rate increased with increasing distance (Figure 3.4), at 8.5m depth, the corrosion rate decreased with increasing distance (Figure 3.5). and at 10.5m depth, the corrosion rate decreases with increasing distance (Figure 3.6).

Figure 3.3: Corrosion Rate at 4.5m Depth

Figure 3.4: Corrosion Rate at 5.8m Depth

Figure 3.5: Corrosion Rate at 8.5m Depth

Figure 3.6: Corrosion Rate at 10.5m Depth

The corrosion rate was calculated based on the original thickness of 9 mm and the remaining thickness. After 10 years of service, the sheet piles at Maydon Wharf Berth 12 exhibited a mean corrosion rate of 0.0416 mm/year.

5. DISCUSSION

The results obtained from the inspections and measurements of the steel sheet piles at Island View Berth 3 and Maydon Wharf Berth 12 in the Port of Durban provided valuable insights into the structural integrity and impact of marine environments on steel corrosion.

5.1. Island View Berth 3

Island View Berth 3 was constructed in 1993 using ARBED BZ 7 steel sheet piles, with an original thickness of 8 mm. Measurements were obtained after 28 years of exposure to the marine environment, and the results revealed a significant variability in the remaining steel thickness across different sections of the berth. The thickness ranged from 3.0 mm to 8.0 mm, suggesting uneven corrosion along the sheet piles.

These measurements showed variability in the corrosion rate across different sections, indicating that environmental conditions, such as exposure to seawater and possibly different chloride concentrations, have varying effects on steel degradation.

5.2. Maydon Wharf Berth 12

The berth was reconstructed in 2012 by using a combination of HZ and AZ 18-700 steel sheet piles. The original thickness of the AZ 18-700 piles was 9 mm. The thicknesses of the sheet piles were measured 10 years after installation at various depths (4.5m, 5.8m, 8.5m, and 10.5m) from the top of the pile to the seabed.

5.2.1. Corrosion Rate Patterns:

- At 4.5 m depth, the corrosion rate decreases with increasing distance from the shore.
- At 5.8 m depth, the corrosion rate increases with increasing distance from the shore.
- At 8.5 m depth, the corrosion rate decreased again.
- At 10.5 m depth, the corrosion rate also decreased with increasing distance.

These scatter plots illustrate the complexity of corrosion processes, which may be influenced by factors such as water salinity, oxygen availability, and tidal changes at different depths.

5.2.2. Average Corrosion Rate

The mean corrosion rate for the sheet piles at Maydon Wharf Berth 12 was 0.0416 mm/year after 10 years of exposure. This average rate aids in estimating the remaining service life of the structure and in planning future maintenance.

5.3. Observations

Both berths exhibited a notable variation in corrosion rates, which likely depended on the environmental exposure, composition of the seawater, and depth of the pile. Corrosion tends to be more severe in areas with higher chloride concentrations and longer exposure to wet-dry cycles owing to tidal movement.

The sheet piles at Island View berth 3, which has been in service for 28 years, exhibit a wide range of remaining thicknesses, indicating advanced corrosion in certain sections. In contrast, the piles at Maydon Wharf berth 12, which were newer (10 years), had a more uniform, but still significant, rate of corrosion.

The corrosion rates at Maydon Wharf Berth 12 revealed that the degradation varies with depth, suggesting that different environmental conditions, such as oxygen and moisture levels, play a role in the rate of corrosion at different levels of the pile.

These results provide essential data for the maintenance and longevity assessment of these structures, enabling port authorities to prioritize repairs and plan interventions to extend the service life of steel sheet piles.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the analysis of the corrosion data from Island View berth 3 and Maydon Wharf berth 12, the following recommendations are proposed:

6.1. Regular Monitoring and Inspections

Given the varying corrosion rates at different depths and locations, it is crucial to implement a more frequent and systematic inspection schedule, particularly in areas with high chloride concentrations or tidal exposure.

Ultrasonic thickness (UT) technology should be used to consistently track changes in steel thickness over time, allowing for more accurate detection of corrosion patterns.

6.2. Targeted Corrosion Mitigation

Apply protective coatings and cathodic protection systems: Given the evidence of depth-dependent corrosion, a combination of coatings and cathodic protection should be applied to areas with higher exposure to wet-dry cycles or higher chloride levels. Cathodic protection systems are essential to prevent concentrated salt-induced corrosion.

Consider zone-specific protection: Each marine zone (atmospheric, splash, tidal, and immersion) has varying corrosion rates. Targeted protection strategies were implemented for each zone, focusing on the splash and tidal zones where corrosion is typically more aggressive.

6.3. Maintenance and Repair Planning

Develop a proactive maintenance schedule: The data suggest that steel sheet piles in areas such as Island View berth 3, which have been in service for more than 28 years, are approaching the end of their service life in certain sections. These areas should be prioritized for repair or replacement before severe structural damage occurs.

Introduce long-term corrosion protection measures: For newly installed sheet piles, invest in long-term protection solutions, such as galvanization, to slow the onset of corrosion and extend the lifespan of the structure.

6.4. Material Selection for Future Installations

Use corrosion-resistant materials: When designing new quay walls or replacing existing sections, materials with higher corrosion resistance, such as corrosion-resistant steel alloys or composite materials, are preferred, particularly in high-salinity environments.

Explore advanced materials and coatings: Investigate the application of innovative materials or coatings, such as epoxy or polymer-based coatings, which have been shown to offer better resistance to marine corrosion.

6.5. Further Research

Conduct environmental impact studies: Further research should focus on understanding the specific environmental factors, such as pH levels, salinity, and temperature variations, that accelerate corrosion at certain depths. This would allow the optimization of protection strategies.

Evaluate the cost-effectiveness of protection methods: conduct a cost-benefit analysis of various corrosion mitigation techniques to identify the most efficient strategies for different zones and conditions in the port.

6.6. Predictive Modeling for Future Maintenance

Use corrosion rate data to develop predictive models: The data gathered from Island View berth 3 and Maydon Wharf berth 12 can be used to create models that predict future corrosion rates, helping the port authorities anticipate when and where maintenance will be required.

Implement a digital monitoring system: A real-time digital monitoring system that integrates corrosion data with environmental factors could help improve maintenance planning and resource allocation and reduce long-term maintenance costs.

By implementing the above recommendations, the Port of Durban can enhance the longevity of its quay walls, reduce long-term maintenance costs, and ensure safe operations.

7. PLAIN LANGUAGE SUMMARY

This study examined how steel sheet pile walls in the Port of Durban are affected by corrosion over time. These sheet piles are important to protect the port from rising water levels and erosion. The remaining thicknesses of the sheet piles were measured for comparison with the original thickness. They corroded at an average rate of approximately 0.0545 mm/y. Some areas wore faster than others did. Our findings will help port managers decide on how to maintain these walls and ensure that they last longer.

8. DICLARATION

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this study. The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. This study did not involve human or animal subjects; therefore, ethical approval was not required. All necessary guidelines were followed to conduct the research. Additionally, this research received no specific grants from any funding agency in public, commercial, or not-for-profit organizations.

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